
UNIVERSITY DIPLOMA PROGRAMME CUMMULATIVE GRADE POINT AVERAGE AS PREDICTOR OF FIRST YEAR UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS PERFORMANCE

By

¹UMUOIGHORO, Barnabas Othuke, Ph.D.

Department of Educational Psychology, School of Education,

College of Education, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria.

correspondence: bbfego@gmail.com

Telephone: +2348032812610

²MEGBELE, Moyioritse Andrew, Ph.D

Department of Educational Psychology, School of Education,

College of Education, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria.

Correspondence: megbeleandrew@gmail.com

Telephone: +2347030619738

OKAGBARE Freedom, Ph.D.

Department of Guidance and Counselling

Faculty of Education

Delta State University, Abraka

09121831782

freedom_okagbare@delsu.edu

Abstract

This study investigated the predictive validity of university diploma programme cumulative grade point average (CGPA) on the first year undergraduate performance. The research stated as its problem determination of the extent to which academic performance in university diploma degree preparatory programme could predict their performance in the first year undergraduate degree programme. In designing the study, the ex-post facto design was employed and secondary data which included the final diploma CGPA of students and their 200 level GPA in the 2012/2013 session were used. Analysis of data was done using the regression and correlation analysis of the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 17. Findings of the study revealed that university diploma programme cumulative grade point average (CGPA) significantly predicted 34.3% of first year undergraduate performance while the degree of relationship (r) stood at 0.588. Further findings from the study revealed that gender differences did not influence the trend in relationship between Diploma Graduate CGPA and the first year undergraduate students GPA. It was concluded that previous knowledge and experiences are important factors that determine the academic achievement of university graduates. The study also submitted that the high or low CGPA of students who were admitted into direct entry from diploma programme may also have been influenced by other variables but not directly affected by gender. It was recommended that academic performance in direct entry preparatory programmes should be set as a standard for admitting students into direct entry programmes in Nigerian universities and universities

should continue to enhance the quality assurance of university diploma programmes so that their predictive validity can be sustained.

Key words: University Diploma Programme, Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA), Predictor, First Year undergraduate, students' performance.

Introduction

According to Shuttleworth (2009), the most common use of predictive validity is inherent in the process of selecting students for university. The modes of admission of candidates into first degree programmes in the universities are in three major forms. These include admissions through the direct entry, admission through the unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) and the pre-degree programme. The admissions through direct entry and the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination are being handled by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) established by the Federal Government of Nigeria through Act 2 of 1978 to regularize the intake of students into the universities and solve the problem of multiple admissions given to some candidates at the expense of others. Conversely, this system has not been able to cater completely for the needs of the populace that crave to get university education in Nigeria. While admission through the pre-degree programme is being handled by the universities themselves thus the Ahmadu Bello University Zaria also established the Interim Joint Matriculation Board (IJMB) programme that acts as a bridge for intending university students to obtain advanced level courses in certain subject areas that will eventually facilitate their direct entry admissions into 200 levels of their various courses of choice. It is important to note that the pre-degree programme in Nigeria is also targeted at bridging the gap for those who are unable to gain admission into their academic programmes in Nigeria universities. The need for the current pre-degree programmes stems from the limited carrying capacities of Nigerian universities which has been estimated to about 350,000 compared to the Millions of applicants that seek university admission annually. This reality in most times have prevented those who often times qualify to be admitted into degree programmes not been admitted. The pre-degree therefore is a platform that equips prospective students for university admission and gives them a good head-start and promote superior studentship in the university whose curriculum is built around those of the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) curriculum.

The programme is targeted to run within one academic session of approximately 6-12 months and its objectives are:

- i. To source superior students for the university's degree programmes and stem the high rate of dropout from the university.
- ii. To ensure adequate preparation of eligible secondary school graduate for university work and
- iii. To enhance analytical and independent learning abilities and promote the intellectual development as well as skills of students.

Odili and Oghuvbu (2015), opined that universities are also empowered through the senate and laws establishing them to mount academic programmes such as diploma programmes with senate approved curriculum and qualified academic and non-academic staff. Universities adopt quality assurance mechanism of the degree programme to the diploma programme. Course outlines are provided for all the courses in the diploma programs and qualified teachers are made to teach them. Lecture time – table is provided for the courses which are taught for a minimum period of 14 weeks per semester. Examination questions are moderated by senior academics to ensure that questions have the required

validity in terms of content. Other quality assurance mechanisms include monitoring of teaching and students attendance at lectures. Examination is also monitored to minimize cases of malpractice and graduates of the diploma programme who pass university entrance qualifying test are offered direct entry admission into 200 level of the degree programme.

Nevertheless, for the past decades some considerable research attention have focused on the examination of the relationship between entry criteria or previous exposure and the subsequent academic performance of students. This relationship has been examined from various angles and levels but the findings of the studies and conclusions on the subject of predictive validity of entry criteria on subsequent academic performance of students are inconsistent, thus making it necessary to study every situation. In the present milieu of this study, it is important to note that the current diploma graduates CGPA could stand as a predictive factor for their academic success in eventual degree programmes in universities. This claim could be justified on the premise that the diploma programme are completely finished and graded before their eventual admission into their degree programmes. On the other hand, it has been established that previous learning experiences are one among the many factors that could influence academic success or learning. Since the diploma CGPA or grade stands as a prerequisite requirement for admission into the university degree programme (Diploma Examination Measures Readiness of Students), it is premised that academic experiences gained from the diploma programme must come to play in determining success or failure during the university degree course. Since admission is done into the 200 level on completion of the diploma programme academic performance is measured at the end of the first and second semester examinations which eventually culminate in the computation of the 200 level cumulative GPA grade at the end of the semester or CGPA at the end of the session. It is on this note therefore, that the present study seeks to carefully investigate the extent to which diploma graduates CGPA contributes in predicting the first year undergraduate (200 level) GPA.

Statement of the Problem

The decay in the Nigerian educational system calls for attention. The search for the most desirable mode of selecting candidates for admission into the Nigerian universities continue. This is evidenced by the public opinion about the standard of students graduating from the universities. The observed mismatch between candidate's performance in the public examinations and their subsequent achievement in university degree examinations has resulted in post University Matriculation Examination (UME) screening exercise and Computer Based Test (CBT). Some educationists have argued that the incompetence of many university students is precipitated by the selection procedure of Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) which fails to control the high rate of examination malpractice, the number and quality of candidates being admitted into the universities annually, hence, universities are coming up with different internally managed programmes such as university direct entry preparatory programme to curb the social menace, as it has been established that previous learning experiences are among many factors that influence student's academic success. The problem of this study therefore, was to determine the extent to which academic performance in university diploma could predict their performance in the first year undergraduate degree programme.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between Diploma Graduate's CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of students admitted through university direct entry preparatory programme?
2. What is the relationship between Diploma graduate's CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through university direct entry preparation programme?
3. What is the relationship between Diploma graduate's CGPA and the first year undergraduate GPA of female students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study.

1. Diploma CGPA of students admitted in the university through the university direct entry preparatory programme does not significantly predict their first year undergraduate GPA.
2. There is no significant relationship between diploma graduates CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.
3. There is significant relationship between diploma graduates CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which diploma graduates CGPA predict first year undergraduate GPA.

Significance of the Study

This research is of great relevance to specialists in educational development and planning, curriculum specialists as well as guidance counselors, as they stand in a position of planning and developing educational programmes that will shape the entire development process of the learners. This will give them an insight into the quality and level of success attained by university diploma as well as insight on how to improve on curriculum development and planning.

This study will also be beneficial to academic staff of tertiary institutions, as it will help them in ascertaining and determining the level of educational development attained by diploma graduates who are admitted into university degree programmes so as to develop strategies that will help them adjust properly into their degree courses. The study will contribute to the pool of limited literatures on those who intend to carry out future research in this area of prediction.

Design of the Study

The research design employed for this study was ex-post facto as investigated and predicted events that have occurred relative to the present, hence no direct influence of the manipulation of the data generated. The study population stood at 893 involving all 200 level undergraduate students who gained admission through direct entry from Delta State University internally managed diploma programmes.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A total of two hundred and twenty four (224) students were purposively selected for this study. The purposive sampling technique is a technique of sampling where the researcher is specifically aware of the target population and the set of persons that are to participate in the

study. The samples thus comprised 25% of the population and were drawn across the various departments of the institute of education where students have been admitted from the internally managed diploma programmes into direct entry.

Instruments for Data Collection

The two instruments used are from secondary data which were drawn from the diploma graduates Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) scores and the first year undergraduate degree Grade Point Average (GPA) scores at the 2012/2013 academic year.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The two instruments were subjected to face and content validation by experts in measurement and Evaluation. The instrument that generated the scores that led to the grade point average and cumulative grade point average (CGPA) has been previously validated and scores standardized by institute of education, Delta State university, Abraka. Hence the instruments were considered to be valid and reliable.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers obtained ethical clearance/ permission from the director of academic records unit of the institute requesting for the diploma graduates CGPA scores and the first year undergraduates GPA scores at the undergraduate degree programme of the 2012/2013 session.

Method of Data Analyses

All data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of the mean, standard deviation while correlation and regression analyses were used to test all stated hypotheses in order to determine the predictive validity of the diploma CGPA scores. The computer software called statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 17 was used for the analyses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results were presented in a chronological order of answer to research questions and the corresponding test of hypothesis.

Research Question One:

What is the relationship between diploma graduates CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of students admitted through university direct entry preparatory programme?

Table 1.1: Relationship between Diploma CGPA and undergraduate GPA.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	Remark
Diploma CGPA	224	3.035	0.5	0.588 ^a	Positively Related
1 st year undergraduate GPA	224	2.80	0.75		

a. predictors: (constant), Diploma CGPA

Table 1.1 reveals that the calculated r which is the correlation factors of 0.588 showed a positive relationship between Diploma CGPA and undergraduate GPA.

Hypothesis One:

Diploma CGPA students admitted in the university through the university direct entry preparation programme does not significantly predict their first year undergraduate GPA.

Table 1.2a: Regression of Diploma CGPA on undergraduate GPA

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	0.588	0.346	0.343	0.60781

a. predictors: (constant), Diploma CGPA

Table 1.2a reveals that the calculated R of 0.588 and adjusted R² of 0.343 showed a positive relationship between Diploma CGPA and undergraduate GPA and that the Diploma CGPA was able to predict 34% of the undergraduate GPA.

Table 1.2b: ANOVA Table for Diploma CGPA on first year undergraduate GPA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	43.361	1	43.361		
Residual	82.014	222	0.369	117.372	0.000 ^a
Total	125.375	223			

a. Predictors (constant), Diploma CGPA

b. Dependent variable: FIRST YEAR UNDERGRADUATE (GPA)

Table 1.2c: Coefficients of Diploma CGPA on First Year Undergraduate GPA.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0.098		0.387	0.699
Diploma CGPA	0.890	0.588	10.834	0.000

b. Dependent Variable: FIRST UNDERGRADUATE GPA

Tables 1.2b and 1.2c presented revealed that the regression indicates a significant F of 117.372 (P<0.05) and a significant calculated t of 10.834 (P<0.05). Table 1.2a also showed that an adjusted R² of 0.343 which implies that 34.3% Diploma CGPA predicted and accounted for the variance in the first year undergraduate GPA. Based on this therefore, the null hypothesis which states that Diploma CGPA of students admitted in the university through the university direct entry preparatory program does not significantly predict their first year undergraduate GPA is rejected. The equation model of relationship based on a straight line graph can therefore be drawn as;

$$y = a + bx + c.$$

$$\text{First year undergraduate GPA} = 0.098 + 0.890 \text{ Diploma GPA} + 0.588$$

Research Question Two:

What is the Relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes?

Table 1.3: Relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	R	Remark
Male Diploma CGPA	103	3.03	0.42	0.788	Positively Correlated
Male Undergraduate GPA	103	2.94	0.72		

Table 1.3 shows that mean Diploma CGPA and undergraduate GPA scores of 3.03 and 2.94 of male students. It also reveals that the correlation factor r of 0.788 indicates that there is a positive relationship between Diploma graduate GPA and First year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant relationship between diploma graduates CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Table 1.4: Test of Significant Relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	r-cal.	r-tab	P-value	Remark
Male Diploma CGPA	103	3.03	0.4					
Male Undergraduate GPA	103	2.94	0.72	102	0.787	0.212	0.00	Significant Relationship

Table 1.4 revealed that the calculated correlation factor (r-cal.) of 0.787 is greater than the tabulated $r(r\text{-tab})$ of 0.212 at ($P = 0.00$). based on this therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between Diploma graduates CGPA and first year undergraduate GPA of male students admitted through direct entry preparatory programme is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the diploma graduates CGPA and first year undergraduate GPA of male student admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Research Question Three:

What is the relationship between diploma graduates CGPA and their first year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes?

Table 1.5: Relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and first year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	R	Remark
Female Diploma CGPA	121	3.03	0.51		
Female Undergraduate GPA	121	2.80	0.71	0.788	Positively Correlated

Table 1.5 showed the mean Diploma CGPA and undergraduate GPA of 3.03 and 2.80 respectively for female students. It also revealed that the correlation factor r of 0.631 indicates that there is a positive relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Hypothesis Three:

There is no significant relationship between diploma graduate CGPA and the first year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Table 1.6: Test of significant relationship between Diploma graduate CGPA and First year undergraduate GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	r-cal.	r-tab	P-value	Remark
Female Diploma CGPA	121	3.03	0.51					
Female Undergraduate GPA	121	2.80	0.71	120	0.631	0.168	0.00	Significant Relationship

Table 1.6 revealed that the calculated correlation factor (r-cal.) of 0.631 is greater than the tabulated correlation factor (r-tab) of 0.168 at ($P = 0.00$). Based on this therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between Diploma graduates CGPA and first year undergraduates GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the Diploma graduates CGPA and first year undergraduates GPA of female students admitted through direct entry preparatory programmes.

Discussion of Results

This study was set out to investigate the predictability of first year undergraduate students' grade point average by university direct entry preparatory programme cumulative grade point average. Findings from the study revealed a significant positive relationship between the Diploma Graduates CGPA and their first year under graduate GPA. Likewise, the result revealed that the diploma graduates CGPA significantly predicted the first year undergraduate GPA of direct entry students, this accounted for 34% variance in the first year undergraduate GPA of the diploma graduates. This observation gives credence to the claim

on the role of previous experiences in the academic performance of students. According to Cota, (1997) students' previous educational learning experiences influenced the current academic performance and second language proficiency of intermediate school limited English proficient students. The submission in this study thus gives confirmation to the study of Odili and oghorbu, (2015), who reported a 31% predictive validity in a similar study commissioned by the senate of the delta state university. Also, ample evidence from literature revealed that the diploma graduate CGPA had a far higher predictive validity on first year undergraduate GPA when compared to other variables such as 8.9% for WASSCE, 4.3% for NECO and 2% for LIME (NERDC, 2007), 10% for UTME (Ojerinde and Kolo, 2010). According to Gue and Holdaway, (2003), the common measure of performance in universities and colleges are the cumulated GPA or the Grade point Average (GPA) for a given semester. Although Pascarella and Terenzini, (2005) submitted that the use of GPA is not a perfect gauge of a student's achievement and learning, the grade point average is useful because it provides a quantitative summary of each semester for a student as well as an overall calculation of the student's performance in all of his or her classes (Whalen, Saunders and Shelly, 2010). The justification of the ability of diploma CGPA to predict the academic performance in their first year undergraduate programme may be from the level of retention attained in related courses done in their diploma programme. This is justifiably supported by the submissions of Campbell and Fuqua, (2009) who noted that several researchers have found GPA to be a predictor of retention and graduation.

The result further revealed no differences in the trend of relationship that existed between the Diploma CGPA and first year undergraduate GPA of male and female students respectively. This observed trend in the performance of male and female direct entry students may give a justification for the earlier claim in relative to the predictability of the undergraduate scores by the Diploma CGPA. By implication therefore, the students are most likely exposed to same learning environment and under the same learning conditions. This observation is not significantly supported by Jacobs, (2002) and Zembar and Blume, (2009) who noted that on the average, girls do better in school than boys. Also, of a contrary view relative to the findings of the present study, Ghazvini and Kharjephour, (2011) submitted that differences exist in the cognitive-motivational functioning of boys and girls in the academic environment, with the girls have a more adaptive approach to learning tasks.

Conclusion

This research based on the major findings concluded that previous knowledge and experiences are important factors that determine the academic achievement of university graduates. The study also submitted that the high or low CGPA of students who are admitted into direct entry from diploma programme may not have been directly affected by gender but influenced by other variables.

Recommendations

In line with findings and conclusion, the research hereby recommends that:

1. Academic performance in direct entry preparatory programmes should be set as a standard for admitting students into direct entry programmes in Nigerian universities.
2. Universities should be consistent to enhance the quality assurance of university direct entry preparatory programmes so as to sustain its predictive validity.
3. During admission, special note should be taken of individual performances in their direct entry programmes so as to help departments and faculties identify students with special academic needs in a bid to helping them attain success in their studies.

References

- Campbell, k. C., & Fuqua, D.r. (2009).Factors predictive of student completion in a collegiate honors program. *Journal of higher education*, 64(2), 123-139.
- Cota, I.C. (1997). The role of previous Educational Learning Experience on current Academic Performance and second Language Proficiency of Intermediate School Limited English Proficient students. *Bilingual research Journal*, 21 (2-3), 147-162.
- Ganzvini, S.D. & Khajehpour, M.(2011). Gender Differences in Factors Affecting Academic Performance of Higher School Students. *Procedia –Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 15.1040-1045.
- Gue, T. & Holidway, U. (2003).*Propensity Score Analysis Statistical Methods and Applications*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Jacob, B.A. (2002). “Where the Boys Aren’t: Non-Cognitive Skills, Returns to School and the Gender gap in Higher Education, *Economics of Education Review*, 21: 589 – 598.
- Odili, J. N & Oghuvbu, E.p. (2015). Performance analysis of Delta State University Diploma in education graduates at the undergraduate level. A Senate Commissioned Research of the Delta State University, Abraka.
- Ojerinde, D. & Kolo, T. N. (2010). Influence of some variables on the degree of predication of first year grade point average (FGPA) by Universities Matriculation Examination (UME) scores. *J. of AEAA* 2, 191-206
- Pascarella, E.T. & Terenzini, P.T. (2005).*How college affects students: A Third Decade of Research* (vol. 2) San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Shuttleworth, R. (2009). Individual Differences in Academic Growth: do they exist, and can we predict them? *Journal of College Student Development*. 47, 101-118.
- Whalen, D., Saunders, K. & Shelly, M. (2010). Leveraging what we know to enhance student performance in colleges. *Journal of Educational Measurement*. 8 (9), 8-98.
- Zembar, M.J. & Blume, L.B. (2009).Gender and academic Achievement. In Zember and Blume (Eds) *Middle Childhood Development: A Contextual Approach*, pp212-215S